

Proposed Law #123: A Law Requiring Each and Every Line Item Budget in the General Appropriation Act to Have One Primary Accountable Public Official

Version 1.0

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The public official must be the primary accountable person for the success or failure of each Project, Program, and Activity (PPA).

For district projects, the primary accountable public official shall be the congressman who proposed or inserted that PPA.

For DPWH projects in a certain locality, the primary accountable public official shall be the highest local DPWH officer of that locality.

For cities and provinces, the primary accountable public official shall be the mayor and governor.

Each primary accountable person, within 45 days after the passage of the GAA, shall execute a notarised document extending the accountability to other professionals, such as engineers for civil works, accountants for audit, etc.

Each contractor of the government project shall still be accountable for the success or failure of their specific projects, since it's awarded to them. However, the citizens of the Republic must also know the public official who proposed or inserted the budget in the GAA.

In case there is an anomaly in the future in the form of a ghost, incomplete, or substandard project, all accountable persons shall prepare evidence proving their innocence.

All ghost, incomplete, and substandard projects shall be strong evidence of guilt against all these accountable people.

"Sa paggawa ng national budget, maraming politician ang laging present. Pero kapag may ghost, incomplete, at substandard project, hugas-kamay sila.

Mahirap malaman kung sino ang accountable sa bawat proyekto. Pero kung ilalagay din sa GAA kung sino ang nag-insert at nag-propose ng line item budget, ay madali itong matutukoy.

Mataas ang chance na matapos ang proyekto kung may accountable person sa bawat line item budget ng GAA."

This proposed law can also be adopted as an ordinance at the local level titled "An Ordinance Requiring EACH and EVERY Line Item Local Budget to Have One Primary Accountable Public Official."

Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in The Great Nation 2025 started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>).

Additional proposed laws will be gradually added in future updates.